

On the Reactivity of *ortho*-Diketonic Groups placed between two Nitrogen Atoms.

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The original object of the investigation was to prepare azine derivatives by the condensation of diphenyl-thio-parabanic acid with *ortho*-diamines.

ortho-Phenylene and 1:2-naphthylene diamines were tried, but, contrary to expectation, it was found that in either case the condensation products contained no sulphur. From this it was clear that the *ortho*-diketo groups, when placed between two nitrogen atoms behave quite differently than when placed between two carbon atoms, as in phenanthraquinone. In order to find out how far this assumption was true, the investigation was extended to some other *ortho*-diketo compounds of the same type, *viz.* dinitro-diphenylthio-parabanic acid, diphenyl parabanic acid, *N*-diphenyl- $\alpha\beta$ -diketopiperazine and dimethyl-oxanilide.

It has now been found that none of them yield the expected azines. The three parabanic acids behave similarly towards the *ortho*-diamines, whilst *N*-diphenyl- $\alpha\beta$ -diketo-piperazine and dimethyl oxanilide are without any action on them.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Diphenyl-thio-parabanic Acid with ortho-Phenylene diamine.

A mixture of diphenyl thio-parabanic acid (1 g.) and *ortho*-phenylene diamine (1 g.) dissolved in pyridine (8 c.c.) was boiled for a few minutes. The separated solid was filtered and crystallised from hot water in fine silky needles, not melting below 300°. It was slightly soluble in alcohol, soluble in hot water, acetic acid or pyridine, and was identified to be phenylene-oxamide. (Found: N, 17.15. Calc: N, 17.28 per cent.).

The pyridine solution, on dilution with water, separated a tarry substance, from which nothing could be isolated. The presence of aniline in the filtrate from the above was proved by diazotisation and coupling with β -naphthol.

1:2-Naphthylene diamine behaved exactly in the same way giving naphthylene-oxamide.

Condensation of Thio-carbanilide with ortho-Phenylene diamine.—The clear solution obtained by heating for three minutes a mixture of thio-carbanilide (3 g.), *ortho*-phenylene-diamine (1.5 g.) and pyridine (3 c.c.), yielded on cooling a solid mass. This was filtered and crystallised from hot water in colourless prisms, m. p. 295-297° (A). It is soluble in alkali but insoluble in acid.

The pyridine solution, on dilution with water, separated a tarry mass which soon solidified on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid. It was purified by crystallization (prisms) from alcohol using a little bone charcoal; m. p. 294-296° (identical with A.)

The substance was identified to be phenylene-thio urea (Found: N, 18.15. Calculated: N, 18.66 per cent.).

The filtrate was diazotised and treated with an alkaline solution of β -naphthol when a red precipitate separated. This was crystallised from alcohol as shining red needles, m. p. 134° and identified to be benzene-azo- β -naphthol.

Dinitro-diphenyl-thio-parabanic acid behaved exactly in the same way as diphenyl-thio-parabanic acid. From its reaction mixture with *ortho*-phenylene diamine, phenylene oxamide and *meta*-nitraniline were isolated.

Condensation of Diphenyl parabanic Acid with ortho-Phenylene diamine.—The precipitate, which separated on boiling for five minutes a mixture of diphenyl-parabanic acid (1 g.) and *ortho*-phenylene diamine (1 g.) dissolved in pyridine (5 c.c.), crystallised from hot water in colourless silky needles, not melting below 300°. The substance was identified to be phenylene oxamide.

The filtrate on dilution with water yielded a white precipitate, which crystallised from alcohol in rectangular plates, melting at 238°. The substance was identified to be *S*-diphenyl-urea. This was confirmed by a mixed melting point determination.

All attempts to condense *ortho*-phenylene-diamine with *N*-diphenyl- $\alpha\beta$ -diketopiperazine and dimethyl-oxanilide even by boiling for one hour in pyridine solution failed and the diketo compounds were recovered unchanged in each case.

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Received September 5, 1927.